

Название публикации: «**LEXICOLOGY IS THE MAIN BRANCH OF
ENGLISH LINGUISTICS**»

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Abstract: What does it mean to know a word? Various linguists have different answers to this very subjective question. To know a word is to enrich one's vocabulary, which in of itself constitutes two major categories: receptive vocabulary and productive vocabulary. The former refers to words that a reader is able to recognize upon encountering them in texts or conversations, while the latter relates to the ability to correctly apply these words in specific contexts such as conversations and writing. Therein lies the aforementioned conflict: is receptive vocabulary sufficient in the context of word knowledge, or does a user also need to attain productive vocabulary in order to claim to know a word?

Key words: lexicology, lexis, word element, words, language, context.

Lexicology is quite simply defined as “the study of lexis, understood as the stock of words in a given language” (Jackson & Amvela, 2007). McArthur (1992) stated that lexicology as a branch of linguistics also deals with the study of nature, meaning, history and use of words and word elements, as well as the critical description of lexicography. In other words, lexicology often requires looking into elements of the language system such as morphology, semantics and etymology. We think that the inclusion of these components in the study of lexis makes lexicology all the more important not just in the context of language study, but also

in larger societal contexts where language use is particularly pertinent. Firstly, the study of lexis inadvertently allows for a deeper and more comprehensive understanding of the entire language system. Lexicology allows us to gain knowledge on not just word formations, but also language components on a more macro level, such as conventional semantic and structural patterns that we often adhere to. This belief stems from the fact that lexical items are building blocks of coherent, meaningful phrases and sentences in a language. As such, lexicology could enable us to gauge conventional semantic and structural patterns that a typical language user would encounter or produce. For instance, in studying morphology, we are able to note the pattern of words containing prefixes like “anti-”, “un-”, “in-” and “dis-” (i.e. undemocratic, inconsolable, disloyal) assert negation or rejection of a particular entity or quality, if not necessarily negative in meaning or connotation. The presence of the suffix “-ly” would typically tell the reader that the word is an adverb, and would exist in a sentence, typically behind a verb, as an adjunct or a complementation. These examples illustrate the conventions that exist in the language that could easily be detected through the study of lexis, which ultimately

enables speakers to use the language more efficiently. We will also argue that the study of lexis is significant in that it emphasises the interrelatedness of linguistic elements within a language system. Any given language would understandably contain a number of words too large to be exacted by humans. Important to note is how these elements don't exist as separate arbitrary entities, but are instead interrelated in how they constitute the richness of a language. Primarily, this refers to how items in the lexicon correlate with one another semantically. As Katamba (2005) stated, there is “an intricate web of relations between the senses of words of a language”. One prime example would be the Componential Analysis, which

serves to capture this interrelation between lexical items by identifying words that contain semantic features which characterise a subject. A word “deer” could relate to other words like “animal” and “herbivore” by virtue of their semantic features. Additionally, this relation could extend even further to similarities in phonology and morphology (homonymy), as well as in semantics, be it parallel (synonymy, antonymy, polysemy) or hierarchical (hyponymy). The establishment of these relational forms in lexicology greatly reinforces how lexical items are often interrelated in spite of apparent form variations, and how this interrelation is crucial in the richness and versatility of the use of language in any context. For instance, “happy” could be substituted with a multitude of synonymous words like “overjoyed”, “excited” and “pleased” to express a blissful feeling of varying degrees. Such a substitution may appear simple, but no less important in demonstrating that the English language is flexible and dynamic, qualities of which make it an interesting language to learn in the first place.

Language evolves over time and does not operate in a vacuum. In other words, language contains not merely a stock of words we commonly understand as lexis or vocabulary, but also the rich history and culture that have helped shape the language into what it is today. The study of lexis as a result becomes important, as it also reflects the background of the groups of people using the language. This encompasses both groups from speakers throughout history as well as in modern times. For instance, the Norman Conquest resulted in the influx of French words

into the English vocabulary in the 13th century, particularly words used in the law courts. As such, we would be able to infer that the speakers from that era who were actively using words like “jury”, “defendant”, “culprit” and “parole” were likely to be people of the upper class who were accustomed to their law courts and judiciary proceedings. In contemporary times, we could also associate the type of lexicon used with certain societal groups. By no means making sweeping generalisations, we may likely find that nominalisation or words with a higher degree of technicality and formality exist at a higher frequency in the lexicon of speakers who are in the upper classes and more educated compared to the rest. Societal members of the middle to lower classes on the other hand may use more simple and direct verb phrases that are easily understood in their everyday use of language. Language and culture are intrinsically bound together, and we believe lexicology allows us to observe how cultural and socioeconomic backgrounds of linguistic groups in society, past and present. Finally, lexicology is important in that it makes language users like us more aware of our choice of words and choose our words more carefully and appropriately. This appropriateness largely concerns the use of suitable language in certain situations and contexts, or when dealing with particular groups of people during communication. Situational or contextual appropriateness refers to whether or not the words used adhere to the setting in terms of formality or technicality. The lexicon used in writing a scientific journal article would differ from that in writing a letter to a close friend in that one would use more formal and technical words in documenting findings and presenting information to the targeted audience. Additionally, in addressing particular societal groups, the choice of lexical items used would also vary considerably. Euphemisms or words that are less crude would be used in favour of direct terminologies with vulnerable groups of people to ensure

pleasantness and political correctness. For instance, phrases like “visually impaired”, “senior citizens” and “academically inferior” would be used in place of “blind”, “old people” and “stupid”, respectively, to avoid unrest. In studying lexis, we are enlightened on how lexical items can have different degrees of formality, technicality and appropriateness. This is especially paramount as it ensures that we as users of language be more mindful of how our words can cause tangible impact in society, and make an effort to speak or write as appropriate as possible at all times.

In conclusion, we firmly believe that the study of lexis is important and not merely for the sake of knowledge. As the saying goes “the pen is mightier than the sword”, so understanding how lexical items function within the language system would enable a more desirable utilisation of words in a language for the betterment of society.

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